

SMART 02

Making and receiving calls with a smartphone

[Start course >](#)

Warsaw University
of Technology

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Google, Android, Google Play,
YouTube and other marks are
trademarks of Google LLC..

SMART MODULE 2

Making and receiving calls with a smartphone

This module describes how to make and receive calls with a smartphone. It adopts a practical hands-on approach and is intended to be a resource for those who work with mobile technology themselves. It can also be used as a reference to help less confident users to make calls on a smartphone.

Intended audience

The intended audience for this module are those who will help learners of all ages to become comfortable with using a smart phone to communicate.

Most of the content in this module is based on Android based smartphones. Other phones will have slightly different screens but the approach will be the same.

Phones help us to stay in touch

Everyone seems to have a smartphone these days. That is not surprising. Smartphones are useful for making calls and staying in touch wherever you are.

But does someone you know feel nervous and unsure about making a call using a smartphone? If so, this module is for you. It provides a step by step guide for those who wish to learn themselves or help others to make calls on a smartphone.

What will you learn in this module

- 1 The different ways that we make phone calls on various types of phones
- 2 How to make and receive calls on a smartphone
- 3 How to make and receive calls using WhatsApp
- 4 How to manage contacts on your smartphone

Chapters in this module

1

Differences when using different phone types

2

How to receive and make a call on a smartphone

3

How to make and receive IP-based calls

4

Managing contacts

SMART

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 1

Differences when using different phone types

Welcome to chapter 1 of the module SMART 02 Making and Receiving Calls: Differences when using different phone types. This chapter describes what is “new” about how a smartphone is used to receive and make phone calls when compared to making a call with a landline or with a cordless phone.

What will you learn

- 1 Understand the steps involved in receiving a call with a landline phone
- 2 Discover how the steps differ between receiving and making a call with a cordless phone and a landline phone
- 3 Understand the steps involved in making a call with a cordless phone
- 4 See how a making a call on a smartphone relates to these two other types of phone

The phone types used for making and receiving phone calls have changed a lot in recent years moving from traditional landline phones to cordless phones and now more commonly to smart mobile phones.

First of all, it is important to recognise that there are some subtle but important differences between making a call using a traditional landline phone compared to using a cordless phone or a smart phone. These differences are not intuitive for all users.

The steps for making a call with a landline, cordless and smartphone are outlined in the next slides and where there are differences these are highlighted for clarity.

Receiving a call with a landline phone

The picture opposite shows a person using a typical landline phone.

Receiving a call with a landline phone involves these steps:

1. the user lifts the receiver from the cradle to answer the call and start chatting to the caller
2. the user can end the call at any time by replacing the receiver on the cradle

Receiving a call with a cordless phone

The picture opposite shows the handset of a typical domestic cordless phone.

When receiving a call with a cordless phone the steps involved are:

1. the user lifts the handset
2. the user **MUST** press the **green** button on the handset to answer the call and start chatting to the caller
3. the user can end the call at any time by pressing the **red** button on the handset

Receiving a call with a smartphone

The picture opposite shows a smartphone.

Receiving a calls using a smart phone is very similar to a receiving a call using a cordless phone.

The details of receiving a call with a smart phone will be described in the next chapter of this module.

First for comparison, let us quickly review the steps involved with making calls on other types of phones.

Making a call with a landline phone

The picture opposite shows a typical landline phone.

When making a call with a landline phone the steps involved are:

1. the user lifts the receiver and waits to hear a **dial tone**
2. the user uses the keypad to enter the number to call – the user will hear the numbers being dialled as they enter them
3. the user then waits for the **ring tone** or an **engaged tone**
4. **engaged tone:** if the user hears an engaged tone (s)he should hang up and may try again later

Making a call with a landline phone (continued)

1. **ring tone:** if the user hears a **ring tone** they wait until either someone answers the call or the phone rings out
2. if the phone rings out and the user is not prompted to leave a voice message (s)he should hang up and may try again later
3. if there is no answer and the recipient has a voice mail set up the user will be prompted to record a message
4. if the user wishes to record a message they may do so and then hang up
5. if the user does not wish to record a message they should just hang up

Making a call with a cordless phone

The picture opposite shows the handset of a typical domestic cordless or phone.

When making a call with a cordless phone the steps involved are:

1. the user lifts the handset
2. the user then uses the keypad to enter the number to call
3. the user **MUST** press the **green** button to activate the phone to dial the number
4. steps 3 to 9 are the same as those for a landline noting that the user can end the call and hang up at any time by pressing the **red** button on the phone

Making a call with a cordless phone (continued)

The main **difference** between making a call with a cordless phone compared to making one with a landline is that when the user lifts the handset and uses the keypad to enter the number to call the user **must** press the **green** call button to actually activate the phone to dial the number they have just entered.

Making a call with a smartphone

The picture opposite shows a smartphone. In SMART module 1 you learnt about some of the icons and images you may tap, touch and slide on the smartphone.. Now we will put that knowledge to good use for making calls with a smartphone.

We have seen that making calls using a smart phone is similar to a making call using a cordless phone. The next chapter will show you how to make a call with an Android smart phone .

This is hands on learning. Do you have a working Android phone but are unsure how to make calls? If so you should get it now to try making calls yourself!

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 1** Differences when using different handset types

The main difference between making a call with a smart phone compared to making one with a landline is that when the user lifts the handset and uses the keypad to enter the number to call they must press the _____ button to actually activate the phone to dial the number they have just entered.
(Type in the colour of the button)

Chapter summary

1

How the way in which calls are made on different phones has evolved

2

The steps involved in making a call on landline phone

3

How calls are made on a cordless phone

4

Comparison of these two phone types with a smartphone with respect to making calls

5

This comparison of how calls are made will help with next chapter on smartphone calls.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

The steps involved in receiving and making a call with a landline phone

2

The steps involved in receiving and making a call with a cordless phone

3

The (subtle) differences between receiving and making a call with a landline and a cordless phone

What is next?

The remaining chapters in this module describe in detail the steps involved in using a **smartphone** to:

- receive and make a call
- receive and make an IP-based call
- manage contacts

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

SMART

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 2

How to receive and make a call on a smartphone

The main use of a smartphone is for making and receiving calls. Users who are used to landline phones may be less confident in managing calls on a smartphone. This chapter provides an overview of smart phone functions to receive calls and call back, with some reference to free Wi-Fi options through different Apps.

What will you learn

1 How to answer or reject a call

2 How to find a missed call

3 How to return a call

Taking a call on a smartphone

One of the key uses of a smartphone is of course to receive calls.

This topic covers the basics of receiving calls using a smartphone.

This is an activity that can be carried out with cooperation from friends and family.

Two ways of taking calls

Actually, depending on whether your phone is locked or unlocked, there are two different ways that an incoming call will appear on your phone.

We will look at both cases.

Process

Incoming call when the phone is locked

If the phone screen is locked, then the call will come up on the screen with the name of the caller. Two buttons will appear on the screen a green and a red button.

Process

1

2

3

Rejecting a call when the phone has been locked

To reject a call in this case you touch the red phone button and slide it up the screen.

You can see that this call is from an unknown caller. It is worth checking this before you decide to answer.

Process

1

2

3

Accepting a call when the phone has been locked
To take the call, you just touch the green phone button and slide it up the screen.

Process

1

2

3

Incoming call when the phone is in use

If you are using the phone and/or the screen is not locked and there is an incoming call, then a small window will appear at the top of the screen with a red and a green button.

Process

Rejecting call when the phone is in use
To reject a call you tap the red phone button

Process

1

2

3

Accepting a call when the phone is in use

To accept the call you tap the green button.

In this case, the user is deciding to accept a call from an unknown number.

Making a call on a smartphone

Another key operation is making a phone call.

Again – it helps if you can work through this task by calling a friend or family member.

Process

1

2

3

4

Using the phone app to make a call

To make a call tap on the green phone icon that is on your home screen in Android..

Process

Screen for making calls

You have now entered the phone app screen for making phone calls.

At the bottom half of the screen is a keypad for entering a phone number. The top half of the screen displays recent calls.

Process

1

2

3

Making a call by typing in a phone number

From here you can make a call in a few different ways.

The more familiar way is to type in the person's phone number and then tap the green button (with the phone icon on it) to make the call.

Process

Making a call by selecting a contact from the calls list

The second way to make a call is to tap on a contact from the list of recently used numbers that are at the top of the screen.

The app will now make a call to that contact.

Finding and returning missed calls

Sometimes you may miss a call or not reach the phone in time and the person who is calling has hung up.

Smartphones are designed to make it relatively easy for you to see who was calling you and to enable you to call them back.

Process

1

2

3

Opening the phone app to find a missed call
To find a call that you've missed you tap the green icon to enter into the phone app.

Process

1

2

3

Finding a missed call

Again you see a list of phone calls in order where the top most call is the most recent call received by the phone. If a call was missed, and you didn't pick up the call all usually the details of the phone call are highlighted in red.

Process

Returning a missed call

To return the call that was missed you tap on that call that is highlighted in red

The app will commence a call to that person.

Some challenges for you...

1. Find the phone icon on the home screen
2. Look at your list of calls/missed calls
3. From the list of previous calls make a call to one of them
4. Next try using the keypad to call one of your friends by typing in their number and pressing the call button

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 2** How to receive and make a call on a smartphone

To answer a call, you slide your finger upwards with the red phone icon

True

False

The image shows a smartphone screen with a black background. At the top, the status bar displays the time 18:36, signal strength, Wi-Fi, and battery icons. Below the status bar is a grey silhouette of a person's head and shoulders, with the text "Private number" underneath. At the bottom of the screen, there are two large circular buttons: a red one with a white telephone handset icon (hang up) and a green one with a white telephone handset icon (answer). Above the green button is a small white upward-pointing arrow. At the very bottom of the screen, there are small icons for mute, speaker, and volume.

Chapter summary

1 Rejecting a call on a smartphone

2 Accepting a call on a smartphone

3 Making a call.

4 Returning a call

5 These are the basic functions related to phone calls on a smartphone.

6 Continued practice of this activity will improve ability and confidence

7 The next chapter will look at making an IP call using the WhatsApp messenger App

8 The next module (SMART module 3) will cover text messaging.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

Understanding Smartphone
telephone **functions**

2

Understanding the **principle** of making calls
using a smartphone

3

Understanding receiving and returning a
call

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

SMART

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 3

How to make and receive IP-based calls

In this chapter, you will learn about the concept of an IP based call. The instructions will guide you on how to use IP-based applications to call family and friends, as well as clients, workmen and suppliers. At the end of the chapter, you will have a chance to practice your learning and apply it to a real-life context.

What will you learn

- 1 The concept of an IP-based call
- 2 How to use WhatsApp to call up to 7 contacts
- 3 How to answer an IP-based call
- 4 How to use WhatsApp to call a contact

The internet has made it easier to communicate with other people. We can use it to send text messages, make voice calls or video calls with family, friends and business contacts.

Different applications can support communication by using the internet. This is done using the Internet Protocol (IP) address, an "Internet phone number" that is assigned to each device connected to the Internet.

There are different applications you can use to make an IP-based call. For this tutorial, we will focus on the 'WhatsApp' one.

WhatsApp Messenger

WhatsApp Messenger is an application that allows users to send text and voice messages, make voice and video calls and share images and documents.

This application runs on mobile devices but is also accessible from computers. The service requires the device to be connected to the internet.

WhatsApp Messenger will be covered in more detail in Module 3 chapter 4.

Did you know?

You do not need to have an email address to use WhatsApp for individual or group calls.

Once downloaded, users can start using WhatsApp by adding their phone number to the App.

Check the next slides to learn how to download and start using WhatsApp.

How to download and start using WhatsApp

Search for WhatsApp on your application store
To start using WhatsApp, if it is not already installed, you need to download and install the application on your mobile device. To start this process, open the Google Play store on your phone.

How to download and start using WhatsApp

Search for WhatsApp

Now search for WhatsApp messenger using the search bar.

How to download and start using WhatsApp

Install and open WhatsApp

Tap on “Install”. Wait for the app to install and then tap on “Open”.

How to download and start using WhatsApp

4

5

6

Agree to the Terms of Service

You will see WhatsApp's welcome page and have a chance to read the Privacy Policy and the Terms of Service. Tap on "Agree and continue".

How to download and start using WhatsApp

Add your phone number

You now need to add your phone number to WhatsApp so people can find you on it.

How to download and start using WhatsApp

Add your name and photo

The next step is to add your name and photo (if you wish to have one on it). Your profile details will allow people to recognize you.

How to download and start using WhatsApp

7

Start using WhatsApp

Great job! You are now ready to use WhatsApp for voice and video calls.

Some tasks for you

Now it is your turn

Download WhatsApp on your mobile device. Install it and create a profile using your phone number. Add a photo (if you wish) and a name to your profile.

How do you feel?

How did you feel working on this task? On a scale from 1 to 10, how difficult was it to start using WhatsApp on your phone? Did you need to ask for help?

Did you know?

IP-based calls are a good way to contact people by just using your internet connection. So you don't need to have phone credit, just access to a Wi-Fi network.

Check the next slides to learn how to call one person or a group of people using WhatsApp.

How to call one person or a group of people using WhatsApp

Making a call using WhatsApp

To make a call using WhatsApp, tap on the tab at the top of the screen named “Calls” and tap on the phone icon with a green background.

How to call one person or a group of people using WhatsApp

Choose the contact and the type of call

WhatsApp will show a list of contacts saved on your phone. These people also use WhatsApp, so you can call them. If you want to make a voice call, tap on the phone icon beside the name of the person. If you want to make a video call, tap on the camera icon.

How to call one person or a group of people using WhatsApp

Making a group call on WhatsApp

WhatsApp also allows you to make group calls. Tap on the option “New group call” and select the contacts you want to participate in the call. You can add up to 7 participants to a group call.

How to call one person or a group of people using

WhatsApp

4

5

Wait for your contact to answer

If you are making a voice call, bring the phone close to your ear and wait for the contact to answer. If you are making a video call, keep looking at the screen until your contact answers. If you want to hang up the call at any time, tap on the red phone icon.

How to call one person or a group of people using WhatsApp

Answering a call on WhatsApp

If you receive a call on WhatsApp, you will see the photo (if the caller has set one up for their profile) and the name of the contact who is calling you. Swipe up the green phone icon to accept the call. Swipe up the red phone icon to cancel/reject the call.

Some tasks for you

Now it is your turn

Call one of your contacts using WhatsApp.

How do you feel?

How did you feel working on this task? On a scale from 1 to 10, how difficult was it to call somebody using WhatsApp? Did you need to ask for help?

Some tasks for you

Now it is your turn

Use WhatsApp to call two of your contacts at the same time.

How do you feel?

How did you feel working on this task? On a scale from 1 to 10, how difficult was it to use WhatsApp for a group call? Did you need to ask for help?

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1** The basic idea of IP calls

- 2** Answering an IP based WhatsApp call

- 3** Making an IP based WhatsApp call using a contact

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 3** How to make and receive IP-based calls

Put the steps of making a WhatsApp call in the correct order:

1. Go to the tab "Calls" and tap on the phone icon
2. Choose the contact and the type of call
3. Wait for your contact to answer
4. Download and install WhatsApp

Chapter summary

In this chapter, you have learned:

1

What is an IP-based call

2

What is WhatsApp

3

How to download WhatsApp

4

How to start using WhatsApp

5

What are the steps for making an individual voice call

6

What are the steps for making an individual video call

7

What are the steps for making a group voice call

8

What are the steps for making a group video call

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

SMART

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 4

Managing contacts

This chapter deals with the use of the contacts list on a smartphone. The contacts list is useful for managing the contact details of your family, friends, clients, workmen and suppliers. This chapter will take a practical approach to this topic and allow you to practice creating and using contacts in your contacts list.

What will you learn

- 1 The purpose of the contacts list on a smartphone
- 2 How to add a contact to a contacts list
- 3 How to find a contact in a contacts list
- 4 How to use the contacts list to make a call
- 5 How to share a contact to a person on your contacts list

Contacts list

With a traditional “landline” phone, you make a call by dialling in the phone number on the phone handset.

In chapter two we saw how you can make a phone call that way on a smart phone too. But you can also make a call on a smart phone by using the contacts list stored on the smart phone.

A contacts list allows you to store the name, number and other details of users you communicate with regularly. If you wish to call anyone in the contacts list, you can simply select their name from the contacts list and call them.

Opening the contacts list and a contact from it

Opening the contacts List

To open the contacts list just tap on the "Contacts" icon. In the image here it is shown as an orange icon with a picture of an outline of a person's bust on it but it may be a different icon on another smartphone.

Opening the contacts list and a contact from it

A contact list

Here is what a contacts list looks like when you have clicked on the 'contacts' icon shown in the last slide.

Opening the contacts list and a contact from it

What the contacts list contains

The contacts list has a list of your contacts' names and their profile picture if they have set that up.

Opening the contacts list and a contact from it

How to open a contact from the list

If you tap once on a name in the list, you can open that contact's details.

Opening the contacts list and a contact from it

A single contact's detail

The contact screen shows the name and details of the contact. Here you can see the surname and first name and phone number.

This screen also enables you to call the person by touching the **green** handset button. Or you can leave this screen by tapping the 'X'.

Challenge: Adding a contact

You can add a contact to the contacts list by clicking on the '+' sign and then entering the name, number and other details of the contact you wish to add.

Let's add in the number for Emergency Services in Ireland, **112**

1. First tap the contacts icon.
2. Now click '+' to create a new contact in your contacts list.
3. Add in the name and phone number of the contact. In this case we will leave the first name box blank
4. In the surname box add in **Emergency Services**
5. Now in the number box - add in **112**.

Did you know?

The European Union has adopted the same number **112** for emergency calls. So wherever you travel across Europe, the same number will put you in touch with emergency services.

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/112>

Practice using contacts

CONTACTS TASK 1

Please use the same steps to add in the contact details of a friend or family member.

CONTACTS TASK 2

Write down the name and phone number of 5 people who you wish to include in your contact list on your phone, then add a new contact into the contacts list on the smartphone for each of them.

CONTACTS TASK 3

Practice using one of the newly created contact details to call someone you know.

Sharing a contact

Smartphones can store a large number of contacts in the contact list.

Sometimes you may wish to share the contact details stored in your contact list with another contact of yours.

The steps to do this are shown in the next slide.

Steps for sharing a contact

1

2

3

Select the contact that you wish to share

1. Open the contact list and find the contact that you want to share
2. Tap the three dots ...

Steps for sharing a contact

1

2

3

Select how to share and the recipient of contact

Select "share" from the menu

Choose who you wish to share the contact with

Choose how you wish to share it e.g. to send it as a message tap text

Steps for sharing a contact

1

2

3

Send the contact

Tap the green button to send the contact

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 4**

A contacts list is equivalent to a phone and address book that you keep beside the phone

True

False

Chapter summary

1

The purpose of a contacts list on a smartphone

2

Adding a new contact to a contacts list.

3

Finding a contact in a contacts list

4

Using a contact to make a call

5

Sharing a contact with a friend.

6

Contact list can be used for helping to make a call – you don't have to remember numbers

7

The contact list is also useful for storing the contact details about a person in one place.

8

Contact list can be used for sending mails and messages as we shall see in SMART module 3

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

Understand the contact list on a smartphone

2

Understand how to find, view and use the contacts list to make a call

3

Understand how to send a contact to another phone

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

Module summary

- 1 The evolution of different types of phones
- 2 Making and receiving calls on different types of phones
- 3 Making and receiving calls on a smartphone
- 4 Making and receiving IP calls using WhatsApp

- 5 Managing contacts on your mobile device
- 6 You should now be able to make and receive calls on a smartphone
- 7 You are now also ready to show others how to do this.

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

Differences when using different phone types

2

How to make and receive a call, also IP-based calls, on a smartphone

3

Managing contacts

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this module or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)